

THE NEW CHALLENGES OF BASIC EDUCATION DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10359733**Julianne Dutra da Costa**

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INTRODUCTION

Education is important, especially the education that is present on the basis of building future knowledge, which begins in early childhood. Elementary school is the period that allows the development of ideas and behaviors, but there are its difficulties.

For Sara Pezzica , (2022, p. 11):

During early childhood education, children's self-regulation capabilities - that is, autonomous regulation - are constantly called upon. During this period, there is an important and gradual transition from the regulation of behavior, mediated by the adult, to greater internal regulation facilitated and supported by the rules and routines of the environments in which they live their journey. Within the school environment, children observe each other and train themselves to put into practice those behaviors that improve coexistence and allow games and activities to be carried out in a group context. They learn to wait their turn to play or use a toy, recognize appropriate behavior to participate in various educational proposals and develop the ability to postpone the impulse to act.

It is believed that one of the best signs that there is good child development would be the fact that the child is showing adequate development and retention of knowledge, which is usually noticeable as he grows. For example, when the child learns to speak, walk, sit and crawl normally. However, this is not always what happens and professionals must be prepared to deal with cases that show signs of disorder and not only prepare, but know how to deal with this new reality in the classroom. Therefore, it is necessary to improve qualified professionals with the aim of learning how to teach children from more recent generations, as the rates are increasing when it comes to children with developmental, behavioral and/or mental disorders.

GOAL

Carry out an analysis of the difficulties faced by elementary school children and show ways to deal with the new reality.

METHODOLOGY

This is a review of content and research , developed with books and data : Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE) - and the collection of *Teacher Training books* , made available by Editora Vozes, whose main objective is to help teachers to understand and allow people with some of these disorders, especially those with higher rates, to have a more efficient basic study .

DEVELOPMENT

In this study, it was observed that a large proportion of children have some type of developmental, behavioral or psychological disorder. According to data collected by the 2010 Census, from IBGE, the prevalence of different types of disabilities and the characteristics of the people who make up this segment of the population were described. As it was a collection of data from participants, the deficiencies were classified by the degree of severity according to the interviewees' own perception of their functionalities. In the end, the Census stated that 8.3% of the Brazilian population had at least one type of severe disability, with 1.4% having mental or intellectual disabilities and the estimate is growing.

We must study and improve ourselves as professionals to be part of this new children's reality through studies and research. Therefore, it is important to update yourself in relation to

studies, including the most recent disorders, such as Autism, also known as Autism Spectrum Disorder, Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) and Oppositional Defiant Disorder.

For Marco Pontis , (2022, p. 9):

The word “autism” comes from the Greek *autos* (“oneself”) and refers to a set of brain development changes that involve an impairment of social, communicative and behavioral skills. Autism spectrum disorders are considered a set (spectrum), as manifestations vary widely in terms of typology and severity.

Disorders such as ADHD and Autism make children prone to presenting comorbidities – disorders other than the one they present, such as learning disorders, there are also behavioral disorders, mood disorders and anxiety –, which make the condition more severe and require a variety of treatments, as they deal with more than one problem within a clinical picture.

For Donatella Arcangeli, (2022, p. 10):

ADHD is a neurodevelopmental disorder, congenital in nature and with multifactorial causes (genetic, neurochemical, anatomical, environmental), which begins around twelve years of age and affects more boys than girls, [...]. The incidence of this disorder is three to four cases for every hundred individuals.

One of the behavioral disorders is mentioned in one of the books (Donatella Arcangeli, p. 11), this being Oppositional-Provocative Disorder (TOP), but the real focus is on Oppositional Defiant Disorder, present in the work translated by Moisés Sbardelotto .

For Gianluca Daffi , (2022, p. 9):

ODD, Oppositional Defiant Disorder, is a behavioral disorder, as is ADHD (Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder). but, unlike the latter, which is included in the category of developmental disorders, ODD has recently been classified as a disruptive disorder (along with Conduct Disorder and Antisocial Personality Disorder). It is a disorder that, with different degrees of severity, concerns a significant percentage of subjects of school age: on average 10 students out of every 100; it generally appears early, to the point where some significant behaviors can already be noticed before the age of 5, even though the period in which the disorder manifests itself in all its complexity is elementary school. It is at this stage that, in addition to the difficulties and challenges typical of age, the dysfunctions resulting from the disorder become more evident and, at the same time, the *limited ability to establish and maintain satisfactory relationships*, which are fundamental for individual well-being.

Despite the difficulties in teaching, basic education is extremely important for adequate child development, which allows the child to grow without further difficulties, therefore,

teachers must increasingly seek new methods, seek to understand new terms, from in the same way that the authors and translators who were part of the Editora Vozes book collection did.

It is important to remember that, even though disorders are scientifically divided equally, one diagnosis is always different from the other. In Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), there are a multitude of issues that need to be taken into account when defining how to work with a child. And with ADHD it is no different. According to ABDA, around 70% of children who have the disorder have other associated comorbidities. Therefore, each child is unique and it will not always be possible for the school to offer standardized treatment by diagnosis. Therefore, it is extremely important that the family, before choosing the school where their child or minor will study, considers the pedagogical issue. What types of adaptations does this school offer? Is there a Specialized Educational Service (AEE), a space where the child can leave the classroom when necessary? Will the child have a companion at these times or not? Remember that inclusion happens when the child is well and happy, but, above all, learning. The participation and monitoring of a psychologist, neurologist and educational psychologist is very important at this very important time for the child's development; and that the possibility of a companion or "facilitator" be introduced, depending on the child's needs, so that the school becomes a pleasant, favorable environment and beneficial for the child's development.

Thus, we come to the conclusion that studying, developing methods and improving these methods is part of what makes the teacher so important in the teaching process and, in addition to teaching, teachers must learn to teach and keep searching for knowledge on an ongoing basis. , in order not to remain inert in the face of the most technological generation of recent times.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

It is concluded that children in the new reality suffer the effects resulting from the increase in the number of children who present some type of disorder, which makes it necessary to establish an increasingly viable school inclusion policy, facilitating effective study for students with some intellectual difficulty, aiming to minimize the impacts of dealing with elementary education, so that they can continue without so many difficulties . Understanding on the part of professionals involved with children reduces in an effective and safe way to deal with emotional shocks, which affect children even at the beginning of the school year, consequently, avoiding future school dropouts . Finally, it is clear that the solution lies in the adoption of new methods and improvement of professionals, to know how to deal with the new

obstacles that emerge in current education, in order to make teaching increasingly efficient and provide a favorable relationship between children and teachers in search of a more inclusive educational policy .

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